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INVESTIGATION OF DELTA-DOPED DOUBLE QUANTUM WELLS

Abstract. The paper investigates the effect of temperature ionization of delta-layer donor impurities on energy levels in a silicon double quantum well with Si Ge 0,8 0,2 barriers. It is shown that the redistribution of charges changes the potential profile, which affects the location and gap between the size-quantized levels. The results can be used for frequency tuning of terahertz optoelectronic devices.

Keywords: quantum well; delta-doping.

The terahertz range of the electromagnetic spectrum is of growing interest due to its potential for optoelectronics. Current devices, such as quantum cascade lasers (QCLs) [1] and quantum well photodetectors (QWIPs) [2], are based on intersubband transitions but are limited to a fixed operating frequency. One solution is delta-doped quantum wells [3], where a narrow layer of donor impurities in the quantum well creates a potential that can be changed by external influences.

In this work, a delta-doped Si double quantum well with Si_{0.8}Ge_{0.2} barriers is theoretically investigated. Geometric parameters: well width 10 nm, barrier in the center of the heterostructure 2 nm, delta layer

thickness 1 nm, surface concentration of donors $N_D = 1.2 \cdot 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. Calculations were carried out using a self-consistent model (Schrödinger, Poisson, electroneutrality equations), as in [3].

Fig. 1 shows the potential profile, energy levels, and their squared wave functions at 4 K and 300 K. As the temperature increases, the impurities ionize, changing the charge distribution and forming an additional V-shaped perturbation, which leads to the rearrangement of well levels and changes in the distances between them. The main attention is paid to the first two levels, the most populated by electrons.

Figure 1. Potential profile (black solid line), positions of the first four size quantization levels (dotted lines) and squares of the corresponding wave functions (dashed lines) for temperatures: a) 4 K; b) 300 K

Temperature ionization allows controlling the energy spectrum – the shift between the first and second levels varies between 0 and 20.2 meV (~ 5 THz). This allows us to change the operating frequency of the device without changing the geometry. The results obtained are suitable for designing spectrally tunable terahertz devices based on silicon nanostructures.

Literature

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ДОСЛІДЖЕННЯ ПОДВІЙНИХ КВАНТОВИХ ЯМ

Демедюк Р., Мезенцева О., Акімов В.

Анотація. У роботі досліджено вплив температурної іонізації донорних домішок дельта-шару на енергетичні рівні в кремнієвій подвійній квантовій ямі з Si_{0,8}Ge_{0,2}-бар'єрами. Показано, що перерозподіл зарядів змінює форму потенціального профілю, що впливає на розташування та зазор між рівнями розмірного квантування. Результати можуть бути використані для частотного налаштування терагерцових оптоелектронних пристроїв.

Ключові слова: квантова яма; дельта-легування.